

LL&YDS
FINANCIALS LIMITED

UNIVERSITY OF
OXFORD

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT WORKSHOP ON DECENTRALISED ENERGY PLANNING IN ZAMBIA

TAJ PAMODZI HOTEL,
LUSAKA, ZAMBIA
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expressed in
this material do
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reflect the UK
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official policies."

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Map of Zambia

1. Introduction

Since February 2023, the University of Zambia in collaboration with the UK Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme has been conducting a pilot study on decentralised energy planning in Zambia. Undertaken by the Decentralised Energy Planning “Special Interest Group (SIG), the pilot aims to complement government efforts in planning and implementing sustainable energy systems to rural and remote communities not connected to the main electricity grid. Specifically, the study aims to formulate prototype guidelines for decentralised energy planning in Zambia. The prototype guidelines will draw on inputs from energy and decentralisation experts, relevant case studies, policy documents and field visits.

So far, preliminary fieldwork undertaken under this pilot study has identified the following as the key constraints to decentralised energy planning in Zambia: i) a lack of clearly established data requirements to support local authorities in decentralised energy planning; ii) a lack of human, technical and financial capacity in local authorities to support district energy planning

and provision, iii) inadequate participation of local communities in energy planning. Drawing on insights from previous workshops, field visits, reviews of country case studies, and ongoing interviews with experts, this pilot study aims at testing the prototype Guidelines for Decentralised Energy Planning in Zambia.

Against this background, a number of activities planned have been undertaken in the past three months (September to December, 2024), key of which was **a workshop at the Taj Pamodzi Hotel in Lusaka on 14 November 2024. The workshop’s main goal was** to brief stakeholders on the Pilot Project currently being undertaken, secure buy-in from the stakeholders, and to discuss the next steps for the successful implementation of the Provincial Action for Community-focused Energy Services (PACE) initiative in Chibombo.

This report highlights the main outcomes of the 14 November 2024 workshop. We have provided a list of persons who were in attendance in Annex A, including information on the positions they hold and the institutions they were representing.

2. Highlights from the Workshop Opening Session

The workshop began with an opening prayer led by the Communications Specialist from Lloyds Financials Limited, Mr Jumbe Ngoma, followed by introductions from all attendees. All the Chiefs present, Government Officials, and other key stakeholders were acknowledged.

The Chief Executive Officer of Lloyds Financials Limited, Professor Lloyd John Chingambo, opened the workshop and acknowledged the presence of important stakeholders, recognising the vital role they were expected to play in not only the PACE Project but also in Decentralised Energy Planning.

He highlighted the fact that the workshop was a critical milestone in the implementation of the Project and how the PACE Project is being implemented by three key institutions—Climate Compatible Growth (CCG), Lloyds Financials Limited, and the University of Zambia—and other stakeholders under the guidance of the Decentralisation Secretariat, under the Cabinet Office and the Ministry of Energy.

He emphasised that Lloyds Financials is leading the implementation in Central Province, particularly in Chibombo, which has been selected

as a pilot location. The Project is intended to serve as a model for potential scaling across Zambia. Its success is crucial for the broader region and the country as a whole. The project commenced in July 2024 and is expected to conclude in March 2025. Stakeholders were encouraged to provide meaningful input to shape the implementation effectively.

Special recognition was given to Royal Highnesses, Government officials from the Central Province Administration, former Members of the National Assembly, the Mayor of Chibombo, District Commissioner of Chibombo and other officials from both Government and institutions, indicating that their participation was recognised as pivotal for guiding discussions.

Professor Stephanie Hirmer (University of Oxford) delivered a welcome address, outlining the significance of the PACE Project in driving equitable and sustainable energy solutions. She provided an overview of the project's timeline and funding, with the first phase ending in March 2025 and subsequent expansions planned until

2030. She highlighted the project's collaboration with the Ministry of Energy and its focus on decentralised energy planning, building on lessons learned from Zambia and neighbouring countries including Kenya.

The Council Chairperson of Chibombo, His Worship the Mayor Newton Nyeleti, delivered the opening remarks on behalf of the Permanent Secretary for Central Province. He began by acknowledging the presence of esteemed Royal Highnesses from Chibombo District, as well as the other stakeholders.

He introduced the project, which aims to pilot the Provincial Action for Community-focused Energy Services (PACE) initiative in Chibombo. Anticipated outcomes include enhanced employment opportunities and community development. The importance of stakeholder input was also highlighted, as this is crucial for ensuring the project's sustainability and enhancing its value. Then the Council Chair declared the meeting officially open, emphasising the transformative impact of the Project.

3. Workshop Sessions and Discussions

3.1 Electrification Status and Challenges

The Senior Energy Officer in the Ministry of Energy, Mr Agnelli Kafuwe, delivered a session on the Electrification Status and Challenges in Zambia, highlighting critical issues in the energy sector. He noted that Zambia's electricity access rate stands at 47%, with rural areas lagging significantly at just 14%. The country's heavy reliance on hydropower, which constitutes 87% of the energy mix, presents substantial challenges, contributing to frequent load shedding.

The government aims to achieve universal access by 2030 through a combination of grid extensions and off-grid solutions such as mini-grids and solar

systems. However, the stark disparity in electricity access between urban areas (87%) and rural areas (14%) underscores the urgent need for decentralised energy planning to ensure equitable progress.

Mr Kafuwe also highlighted Zambia's energy consumption profile, where biomass accounts for 71%, followed by oil (14%), electricity (11%), and coal (2.9%). The impact of load shedding is profound, disrupting vital sectors such as agriculture, mining, and business, and significantly reducing productivity.

Achieving universal electrification will require decentralised energy generation strategies and

active collaboration with traditional leaders to ensure inclusive and sustainable energy solutions.

3.2 Decentralised Energy Planning Guidelines

In the second presentation Dr Mashekwa Maboshe, a Senior Lecturer at the University of Zambia, made a presentation that emphasised that the decentralisation of energy services is a key focus area. In the presentation he indicated that a guiding document, the Electricity Sector Public-Private Guidelines Framework – also referred to as the Energy Sector Devolution Plan – provides strategic directions for this process, placing a strong emphasis on decentralised energy investments at the local level.

The presentation highlighted collaborative efforts between the University of Zambia, the University of Oxford, and the FCDO-funded CCG programme, which have operationalised the Prototype Guidelines for Decentralised Energy Planning in Zambia. He indicated that a notable initiative in the Guidelines is the establishment of district energy coordination roles to address gaps in technical expertise and accountability in energy planning at the district level; hence the need for the establishment of the office of District Energy Coordinator in every district in Zambia. He emphasised that these Coordinators will act as a bridge between various stakeholders, including local councils and utilities such as ZESCO.

Dr Maboshe also introduced the recommendation to establish community-based Energy Planning Extension Officers. He indicated that these officers will play a crucial role in raising awareness about clean energy, serving as local energy champions, and addressing the lack of understanding about energy services within communities.

3.3 PACE Project Overview

In his presentation, Mr Ronald Daka, a Director at Lloyds Financials Limited and the PACE

Pilot Project, provided an in-depth overview of the PACE Project, underscoring its focus on integrating decentralised energy generation into government policy. He informed the workshop that the Pilot Project prioritises rural electrification as a means to improve quality of life and promote equitable development in areas that are currently underserved due to the limitations of the national grid in reaching rural areas. He emphasised that this was a key reason behind the need to have more decentralised systems such as mini-grids, solar home systems, and local renewable energy projects as practical and necessary solutions.

Mr Daka further highlighted the Project's emphasis on empowering local communities to take charge of planning and implementing energy initiatives in their jurisdictions. He indicated that through decentralising energy planning districts are encouraged to use their local strengths or areas where the district has comparative advantages, including availability of local resources such as waterfalls for hydroelectricity and solar potential for mini-grids. The presentation pointed out the need for collaboration with traditional leaders, community organisations, and district administrations as deemed essential for the success of these initiatives, with Chiefs and local councils playing a crucial role in fostering community ownership.

The presentation also indicated that the initiative aims to strengthen local government capacity by establishing District Energy Offices and recruiting community-level Energy Planning Extension Officers, whose roles were designed to ensure that local energy plans are effectively integrated into National Plans through the Integrated Development Planning processes.

Mr Daka how crucial it is to implement robust monitoring and evaluation frameworks to maintain transparency, accountability, and adaptability throughout the project.

The presentation concluded by drawing attention to the alignment of decentralised energy planning with Zambia’s broader decentralisation reforms, particularly constitutional mandates such as Article 148, which empowers communities to take an active role in developmental decision-making.

“By failing to prepare, you are preparing to fail. Planning is bringing the future into the present so that you can do something about it now” – ALAN LAKEIN

3.4 Group Discussion: Case Studies

The workshop included breakout sessions that centred on four case studies, all about different community energy initiatives, e.g., irrigation or telecommunications, that could be prioritised in a district energy plan. The purpose of the case studies was: (1) to identify the roles and responsibilities of key stakeholders in implementing energy projects, (2) to understand the key steps to implement the project, and (3) to consider how the proposed projects could be funded. Below are some of the key takeaways:

GROUP 1

- i. Group 1 began their discussion by outlining their case study, which focused on increasing irrigation development to improve crop yields for small-scale farmers and reducing post-harvest losses through cold chain storage. They emphasised two main points: the processes involved in such projects and the governance systems within the food and agricultural sector. Their discussion provided a detailed overview of the critical steps required to implement successful agricultural development initiatives.
- ii. The group stressed the importance of stakeholder engagement in the process, identifying key stakeholders such as

local authorities, Chiefs, ZESCO, Zambia Environmental Management Agency (ZEMA), the Rural Electrification Authority, and community groups. They highlighted the necessity of involving a diverse range of stakeholders, including women, youth, and differently-abled individuals, to ensure inclusivity in the project. Early identification of stakeholders, followed by engagement, was deemed essential for addressing their needs and gaining their support.

- iii. A comprehensive feasibility study was identified as a critical component of the project. Group 1 emphasised the need to consider factors such as community needs, affordability, social acceptability, and the potential for rural electrification. They also stressed the importance of assessing the economic activities in the area and the number of beneficiaries to ensure the project's viability. The feasibility study should be detailed and include considerations such as the environmental impact of the project, which requires engagement with ZEMA for the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) process. The group also noted the need for construction permits from the Energy Regulation Board, especially for solar-powered mini-grids, which would play a key role in improving productivity.
- iv. In terms of governance, the group discussed the existing agricultural activities in the area and suggested learning from other districts and previous initiatives. They highlighted the need to understand what crops are being grown, how much is being produced, and how food systems are structured within the community. Group 1 also emphasised the role of local food policy councils and suggested that the project should align with existing food policies to ensure coordinated efforts. They pointed to previous initiatives, such

as solar hammer mills, as valuable learning opportunities for improving future projects.

- v. The group outlined several funding options for the project, identifying the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) as a potential source of support, as well as other international and local partners. The role of civic leaders, such as mayors, in helping to connect the project with potential funding sources was also highlighted. Additionally, the group noted the potential for using the Constituency Development Fund (CDF), as well as commercial and development banks, which have previously supported irrigation and solar projects.
- vi. In summary, Group 1's presentation provided a comprehensive approach to improving agricultural productivity and sustainability through irrigation development and post-harvest loss reduction. They emphasised the importance of stakeholder engagement, detailed feasibility studies, understanding governance systems and learning from past initiatives. The group also discussed various funding avenues, highlighting the role of civic leaders in securing financial support. Their ideas offer a practical framework for implementing agricultural development projects that are inclusive, sustainable, and responsive to the needs of small-scale farmers.

“Community leaders hold the influence to either steer a project towards success or shift its course entirely”

GROUP 2

- i. Group 2 focused their discussion on the establishment of more markets, identifying this as a crucial missing component in Zambia. They emphasised that markets

serve as centres for trade and opportunities within the value chain, benefiting local communities. The group identified two key components for the successful establishment of markets: stakeholder engagement and feasibility studies.

- ii. Stakeholder engagement was highlighted as a critical first step. The group stressed the importance of ensuring local stakeholders are involved from the beginning of the project, particularly when selecting the location for the market. They argued that having stakeholder buy-in is essential, as it helps prevent potential issues once the market is established, e.g. vandalism. Furthermore, they noted that political challenges could arise when identifying beneficiaries for the market, but good stakeholder engagement can mitigate these risks. The group recommended ensuring that the beneficiaries were known and involved before construction begins to avoid political conflict during the later stages of the project.
- iii. The second crucial point raised was the importance of conducting a thorough feasibility study. The group emphasised that a well-conducted feasibility study serves as the backbone of the project, as it identifies whether the idea is viable or not. A key element of the feasibility study is identifying the suitability of the location, ensuring the local community is in agreement with the project, and determining what commodities will be available for trade. They highlighted the importance of matching the market with the needs of the local community; for example, establishing a dairy-focused market in a dairy-producing area rather than introducing irrelevant products like avocados. The group argued that failure to conduct a comprehensive feasibility study often leads to projects being abandoned or becoming "white elephants".

- iv. Energy requirements were also discussed, with Group 2 emphasising the need to choose the appropriate type of energy based on the activities within the market. This is another factor that should be included in the feasibility study. They pointed out the role of ZEMA in the process, noting that a proper environmental and social impact assessment must be conducted to avoid complications, such as project shutdowns by ZEMA due to non-compliance with regulations. Waste management and pollution control were also mentioned as key considerations.
 - v. The group briefly touched on funding, mentioning the CDF and the Vision Fund as potential sources of financial support. The Vision Fund, in particular, was noted for offering low-interest loans, which is a rare opportunity compared to the high borrowing rates typically seen in commercial banks.
 - vi. In summary, Group 2 highlighted the importance of stakeholder engagement and feasibility studies in establishing successful markets for trade and opportunities. They underscored that proper planning and consultation with local communities, government, and other stakeholders are critical to avoiding failures and ensuring the project meets the needs of the community. Their discussion provided valuable insights into the key factors that contribute to the success of market development projects.
- ii. The group began by highlighting the importance of electricity for the telecommunications towers and associated infrastructure. They pointed out that the project's success hinges on high-level support, specifically from the President of the Republic of Zambia. Achieving buy-in at the highest level was described as essential, as it would allow the project to be seen as a policy initiative, facilitating its smooth implementation and addressing any potential funding challenges.
 - iii. To secure such high-level buy-in, the need to engage with a range of stakeholders was emphasised. They identified the Ministry of Local Government and Rural Development as particularly critical to the project's success. According to the group, focusing on key figures such as the district commissioner, the provincial secretary (PS), and the provincial local government officer would help elevate the project's profile and ensure alignment with national priorities. Engaging with the Presidential Delivery Unit was also considered a vital step in the process, as it would eventually enable direct access to the President's office and facilitate the issuance of a presidential directive.
 - iv. The second major point discussed was the importance of securing funding, particularly through the CDF. However, the group cautioned that for the project to be funded through this channel, the local infrastructure across the chiefdoms in Chibombo District. The group's main focus was on ensuring effective communication and information access in the region. Two crucial components to the success of the project were identified: roles and responsibilities, and obtaining the necessary buy-in from key stakeholders.

“Historically, projects that have excluded chiefs and traditional leaders have often failed due to a lack of ownership and buy-in of the project”

GROUP 3

- i. Group 3's discussion centred around the construction of mobile telecommunications

Member of Parliament (MP) must be fully committed to supporting the initiative. If the MP does not endorse the project, it would be difficult to secure the necessary funding from the CDF.

- v. In summary, Group 3's presentation focused on the vital steps of obtaining buy-in from

high-level authorities and local stakeholders, with a particular emphasis on the President's support and the involvement of local MPs for funding purposes. These elements were identified as essential for ensuring the successful construction and operation of mobile telecommunications infrastructure in Chibombo District.

4. Next steps

The next steps for the successful implementation of the Provincial Action for Community-focused Energy Services (PACE) initiative in Chibombo should begin with engaging the community and relevant stakeholders. It is crucial to clarify the roles of local authorities, Chiefs, and community leaders to ensure the energy solution aligns with their needs. The next step is to identify the specific locations and energy requirements of the communities, ensuring the project addresses their priorities.

Following this, community sensitisation should take place, ensuring all stakeholders, including headmen, understand the project's objectives. Before starting sensitisation, it is vital to have a clear understanding of the community's needs and the project's intended outcomes. Involving local leaders and community members in the

process will foster a sense of ownership and ensure the project meets their needs.

Once sensitisation is complete, the project should seek validation and endorsement from community leaders, particularly Chiefs and headmen, who will assist in securing land and resources. If the feasibility study has identified potential sites, these should be presented for community feedback. This endorsement will solidify the community's commitment to the project and help identify the resources required, such as funding from the CDF or other appropriate sources.

In summary, the next steps include engaging stakeholders, validating the feasibility study with the community, and securing necessary resources, laying the groundwork for a successful and sustainable energy project.

5. Closing remarks

The closing remarks were given by Dr Nswana, the Assistant Director of the Decentralisation Secretariat at Cabinet Office. He emphasised that Decentralisation is here to stay, as outlined in Article 147 of the Constitution. Dr Nswana encouraged stakeholders to support the PACE Project, especially given the current electricity crisis, and highlighted the need for better

planning and infrastructure development. He stressed the importance of involving all stakeholders in the process, using the concept of a "Container of Stakeholders" to ensure inclusivity. He also urged the team to enhance consultations and involve Chiefs for project success. Dr Nswana concluded by thanking everyone again for their involvement.

APPENDIX

Annex A: List of workshop attendees

No.	Name	Institution/Role
1	Mashwekwa Maboshe	UNZA - Lecturer and Researcher
2	Albert Ngosa	LGAZ - Research Officer
3	Stephanie Hirmer	Oxford University - Associate Professor
4	Moni Kaczmarska	UCL/CCG - Research Assistant
5	Mwenya Muyeba	Private Sector -Journalist
6	Odesi Muleya	REA - Senior Engineer Projects
7	Lisuba Kabanda	Chiefs Affairs - Senior Chiefs Affairs Officer
8	Mazuba Brave	D/Admin Chibombo - District Admin Officer
9	Grace M. Kanyata	Chibombo Town Council - Council Secretary
10	Dr. Nswana Movens	Cabinet Office Decentralisation - A/Director
11	Mumba Shambayi	Ministry of Energy – SEO
12	Mubanga Lupale	Chibombo Town Council - Director Planning
13	Lloyd Chingambo	Lloyds Financials Limited – CEO
14	Kaonga Lawrence	Ministry of Local Government & Rural Development - Provincial. Chiefs Affairs Officer
15	Elizabeth Banda	Ministry Of Finance & National Planning - AG PPIA
16	Mbololwa Subulwa	FPAZ - Vice President
17	Raymond Muyovwe	ERB – Statistician
18	Agnelli Kafuwe	Ministry Of Energy – SEO
19	Jumbe Ngoma	Lloyds Financials Limited - Communication For Development Specialist
20	Annalicia Sitali	Tech-Analytics – BDO
21	Evelyn Musonda	LCC - Senior Com. Dev Officer
22	Mukangulu Johnpal	PDU - Principal Planner
23	Emanuel Simpasa	Lloyds Financials Limited -
24	Newton Njellah	Private Sector -Journalist
25	Alexander Chileshe	UN-Habitat
26	Ephraim Belemu	FPAZ - The Former Chair - Parliamentary Committee on Energy
27	Erick Mukwita	Chibombo Town Council -
28	Chembo Sichinga	ERB - Manager-Renewable Energy
29	Peter Lundi	Chibombo Town Council
30	Ceaser Sakuwunda	Chibombo Town Council
31	Mandumwa Harrington	Chibombo Town Council
32	Chief Liteta	Royal Highness
33	Chief Chitanda	Royal Highness
34	Chiefteness Mungule	Royal Highness
35	Lynnly Mayenga	Lloyds Financials Limited - Operations Manager
36	Ronald Daka	Lloyds Financials Limited – Director, LOGIP

Annex B: Workshop Agenda

Venue: The Pamodzi Hotel, Lusaka

Date: Thursday, 14 November, 2024

Time: 8:30–13:00, followed by lunch

Moderator: Lynnly Mayenga

Time	Activity/Item	Responsible
08:30–09:00	Arrival and Registration	Lloyds Financials
09:00–09:10	Workshop Opening, Special Welcomes & Prayers	Lloyds Financials
09:10–09:20	Introductions	All
09:20–09:30	Welcome Remarks	
09:30–10:30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Project Overviews: ■ Electrification status in Chibombo (5 mins) ■ DEPZ Guidelines (10 mins) ■ PACE Project (10 mins) ■ Q&A 	CCG/UNZA/Lloyds
10:30 - 10:45	Health Break	
11:00 - 12:30	Group Discussion: Roles, Responsibilities & Funding for Local Energy Initiatives	All
12:30 - 13:00	Group Feedback & Consolidated Report	All
13:00 - 13:05	Discussion: Next Steps and Action Points Workshop Close	Moderator
13:00 - 14:00	Lunch and Networking	All

Annex C: Pictures

Picture of the Royal Highnesses arrival from Chibombo District at Taj Pamodzi Hotel, Lusaka, for the workshop.

Photo of the opening remarks and official declaration by His Worship Newton Nyeleti, Council Chair for Chibombo.

Picture taken during the workshop as presentations were being made.

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